

Spectrophotometric Determination of the Stability Constant of Cobalt(II)-nitroso R-Salt Chelate

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A spectrophotometric method has been developed for determining the stability of cobalt-nitroso R-salt system which forms a reddish yellow 1:3 chelate. The theoretical considerations underlying the method have been adopted from those of Anderson *et al.*¹ and Dey *et al.*² who have described a method for 1:1 and 1:2 complexes but no explanation seems to have been put forward by them for 1:3 complexes. Considering a reaction of the type:

for the above reaction, the formation constant is given by the expression :

$$K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-3x)^3}$$

To evaluate the concentration of the complex, 'x', two concentrations of 'a' and 'b' are involved, which can be expressed as

$$K = \frac{x}{(a_1-x)(b_1-3x)^3} = \frac{x}{(a_2-x)(b_2-3x)^3}$$

The above equation has been solved and one of the real values of 'x' has been found to be

$$\left(\frac{-G + \sqrt{G^2 + 4H^3}}{2} \right)^{1/3} + \left(\frac{-G - \sqrt{G^2 + 4H^3}}{2} \right)^{1/3} - \frac{A_1}{3}$$

where G, H, and A₁ are defined in terms of 'a₁', 'a₂' and 'b₁' and 'b₂' by the following relations:

$$G = \frac{a_2 b_2^3 - a_1 b_1^3}{27(a_1 + b_1 - a_2 - b_2)} + \frac{2A_1^3}{27} - \frac{A_1}{3} \left[\frac{(b_1^3 - b_2^3) + 9(a_1 b_1^2 - a_2 b_2^2)}{27(a_1 + b_1 - a_2 - b_2)} \right]$$

$$9H = \frac{(b_1^3 - b_2^3) + 9(a_1 b_1^2 - a_2 b_2^2)}{9(a_1 + b_1 - a_2 - b_2)} - A_1^3$$

and

$$A_1 = \frac{3(a_2 b_2 - a_1 b_1) + (b_2^3 - b_1^3)}{3(a_1 + b_1 - a_2 - b_2)}$$

1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1195; 1949, 71, 908, 912.
2. *Proc. Symp. Chem. Co-ordination Compounds*, Agra, 1959, 2, p. 168.
3. *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, 6, 314; *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 19, 324.

The values of ' x ' have been calculated from the experimentally determined values of ' a_1 ' and ' b_1 ' and ' a_2 ' and ' b_2 ' and knowing the values of ' x ', K was evaluated from the above equation. The average value of $\log K$ was found to be 13.3 at 25°, which is in agreement with those obtained by the mole-ratio method, $\log K = 13.9$.

The details of the method and experimental methods involved will be published elsewhere.

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